

SOME PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY

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Abstract: The article discusses the techniques for replenishing the vocabulary of students of non-linguistic universities. It determines the methods of semantization that are adequate to the terminological vocabulary.

Some ways of enriching the vocabulary of the language are considered: international words, affixation, synonyms and antonyms. The stages of work for consolidating juridical lexis are given.

Key words and phrases: terminological competence, semantization, international words, affixation.

Introduction

The main way of training the organization of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia is the preparation of a competent, responsible employee of internal affairs bodies, capable of effective work in their specialty at the level of international standards. An important role is played by the role of linguistic culture and the development of competent use skills by employees.

ATS of a foreign language in the representation of life as a means of a professional society. In addition, knowledge of a foreign language affects logical thinking, trains memory, develops mental abilities, promotes intellectual development and improvement of individual and professionally significant qualities.

Scientists in the field of foreign language teaching methods believe that practical knowledge of a foreign language means the formation of intercultural competence, that is, the ability to carry out speech activity and interact in situations of intercultural communication. Consequently, in the process of teaching a foreign

language, students should develop the skills of intuitively correct use of lexical and grammatical units, as well as units of non-verbal communication. We are talking about the formation of terminological competence

The object of the research is the methodology of teaching foreign language vocabulary, in particular teaching terminological legal vocabulary. The subject of the study is English.

The appeal to the English language is explained by the fact that, firstly, English is one of the most commonly used languages in the world and, secondly, knowledge of the English language is certainly necessary for police officers, since they are involved in security public order during various cultural and sporting events of international level. Thus, the ability to speak English can be interpreted as a tool for the professional and personal development of an individual.

Let us note that the problem of teaching vocabulary remains one of the most pressing problems in the methodology of teaching a foreign language at a non-linguistic university. This is due to the fact that "... language is the most important means of communication and influence, a mechanism for obtaining and processing information, a means of optimizing all types of human activity, and jurisprudence and legal activity belong to the sphere of increased speech responsibility". In our opinion, one of the conditions for active language acquisition in accordance with the practical needs of professional activity is the mastery of special terminological vocabulary, since, as the analysis of empirical material shows, it carries the greatest informative load.

Therefore, adequate knowledge of terminological vocabulary is one from general issues of linguistics. Language and law. the main conditions for understanding a particular discursive utterance. It is known that vocabulary is remembered better if it is introduced systematically. Systematicism is understood as one of the fundamental properties of the organization of the world.

A. A. Ufimtseva rightly asserts that "the human mind reflects real reality with all its inherent systemic connections and relationships that are objectified in language"

In this case, it is especially important to determine methods of semantization that are adequate to the terminological vocabulary.

As teaching practice shows, the methodology for working with legal vocabulary conventionally includes four stages. The first stage consists of a systematic grouping of terms into categories of concepts.

In the semantization of terminological vocabulary, it is also important to correctly interpret the sense of international words. Let us remind you that international words are words that are found in more or less the same sound form, grammatical design and semantic content in a number of languages. International words are often called internationalisms, which are understood as “lexemes, similar to the degree of identification graphically or phonemically with fully or partially common semantics, expressing concepts of international significance and coexisting in several (almost no less than three) synchronically comparable languages (including unrelated or not closely related)”.

Based on the above, the second stage of teaching terminological vocabulary involves the correct interpretation of international words. Interpretation of international words in English and comparison of them with the corresponding Russian equivalents shows that in Russian they are mostly monosemic (unambiguous)

Conclusion

In English, compared to Russian, many international words are polysemic. They have a wider range of meanings, i.e. we are observing the so-called expansion of lexical connotation.

The third stage of work on developing terminological vocabulary is aimed at interpreting the semantics of affixation - the formation of cognate words using suffixes and prefixes. Affixation is another one of the most productive ways to enrich the vocabulary of the English language. According to O.D. Meshkov, the semantics of English affixes are clear. Let us note that knowledge of the semantics

of affixes contributes to the development of the language guessing skill necessary for reading special (legal) literature without a dictionary. Let's look at examples:

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